

Unsupervised 4D myocardium segmentation with a Markov Random Field based deformable model

L. Cordero-Grande^{*a}, G. Vegas-Sánchez-Ferrero^a, P. Casaseca-de-la-Higuera^a, J. Alberto San-Román-Calvar^b, Ana Revilla-Orodea^b, M. Martín-Fernández^a, C. Alberola-López^a

^aLaboratorio de Procesado de Imagen, Escuela Técnica Superior de Ingenieros de Telecomunicación, Campus Miguel Delibes s.n., 40011, Valladolid, Spain.
Phone: +34 983 423660 ext. 5590. Fax: +34 983 423667. (<http://www.lpi.tel.uva.es>)

^bServicio de Cardiología, Hospital Clínico Universitario, Avda. Ramón y Cajal 3, 47005, Valladolid, Spain.
<http://icicor.es>

Abstract

A stochastic deformable model is proposed for the segmentation of the myocardium in Magnetic Resonance Imaging. The segmentation is posed as a probabilistic optimization problem in which the optimal time-dependent surface is obtained for the myocardium of the heart in a discrete space of locations built upon simple geometric assumptions. For this purpose, first, the left ventricle is detected by a set of image analysis tools gathered from the literature. Then, the segmentation solution is obtained by the Maximization of the Posterior Marginals for the myocardium location in a Markov Random Field framework which optimally integrates temporal-spatial smoothness with intensity and gradient related features in an unsupervised way by the Maximum Likelihood estimation of the parameters of the field. This scheme provides a flexible and robust segmentation method which has been able to generate results comparable to manually segmented images for some derived cardiac function parameters in a set of 43 patients affected in different degrees by an Acute Myocardial Infarction.

Key words: Magnetic Resonance Imaging, Markov Random Field, unsupervised segmentation, cardiac function, Acute Myocardial Infarction

Acronyms

AAM	Active Appearance Models	ESV	End Systolic Volume
AC	Active Contours	FGMM	Finite Gaussian Mixture Model
AMI	Acute Myocardial Infarction	GSA	Gibbs Sampler Algorithm
ANOVA	Analysis of Variance	LA	Long Axis
ASM	Active Shape Models	LV	Left Ventricle
CC	Cardiac Cavity	MAP	Maximum a Posteriori
ED	End Diastole	ML	Maximum Likelihood
EDV	End Diastolic Volume	MM	Myocardial Mass
EF	Ejection Fraction	MPM	Maximization of the Posterior Marginals
EM	Expectation-Maximization	MR	Magnetic Resonance
ES	End Systole	MRF	Markov Random Field
		MRI	Magnetic Resonance Imaging
		MT	Myocardium Thickness
		PVE	Partial Volume Effect
		RV	Right Ventricle
		SA	Short Axis
		SNR	Signal to Noise Ratio
		SPECT	Single-Photon Emission Computed Tomography

*Corresponding author

Email addresses: lcorgra@lpi.tel.uva.es (L. Cordero-Grande),
gvegsan@lpi.tel.uva.es (G. Vegas-Sánchez-Ferrero),
casaseca@lpi.tel.uva.es (P. Casaseca-de-la-Higuera),
asanroman@secardiologia.es (J. Alberto San-Román-Calvar),
arevillaorodea@gmail.com (Ana Revilla-Orodea), marcma@tel.uva.es
(M. Martín-Fernández), caralb@tel.uva.es (C. Alberola-López)

1. Introduction

Cardiac imaging is nowadays one of the most valuable tools in helping diagnosis, treatment and follow-up of cardiac pathologies, as it provides qualitative and quantitative information of the heart that would be impossible to obtain otherwise. Among the imaging techniques for cardiac examination, MRI is now a well-established (although still advancing) modality which provides both anatomical and functional characterization of the heart (Frangi et al., 2001). It has been adopted as a *de facto* standard in functional studies due to its superiority in spatial resolution and SNR compared to other non-invasive techniques such as echocardiography (Schalla et al., 2001), whereas invasive techniques such as SPECT have been primarily intended for myocardium perfusion studies (Ioannidis et al., 2002).

Quantitative functional analysis of the heart is performed by the extraction of some cardiac descriptors which can provide information of both global function (LV Volume, EF, Cardiac Output, MM) and local motion and deformation (Wall Thickening) (Frangi et al., 2001). LV Volume stands out as one of the most important descriptors, since it is the starting parameter to derive other indices related to the LV function. Its calculation, as it is the case for many other parameters, involves an appropriate 3D segmentation of cardiac chambers as a prerequisite. Many clinical studies still rely on manual delineation of the myocardium, but this procedure is very tedious and prone to intra- and inter-observer variability. The fact is that, specially in clinically relevant cases, the available computer tools for marking the contours do not provide a fully-automated segmentation procedure or require a training stage to achieve precise measurements. The present method is a contribution to fill in this gap, as it has been designed to automatically obtain accurate and robust functional measurements of the cardiac activity in an unsupervised way within a clinical environment.

1.1. State of the art in cardiac segmentation

MR cardiac images present a number of features that make them difficult to segment. Even in noiseless cases, they may present blurred edges due to the PVE and can be affected by motion artifacts. In addition, low contrast between the myocardium and surrounding tissues complicates the segmentation further. This is the case of the papillary muscles, the trabeculae or the liver, the intensity of which is virtually indistinguishable from that of the myocardium. The segmentation procedure has to consider the variability in the external surrounding tissues as well as in the contrast of the images. Moreover, it has to be flexible enough to adapt itself to the geometric and dynamic features of different subjects, which is even more relevant in the presence of pathological cases. This makes fully automatic construction of a 4D heart model a very complex task, even more given the usual low image resolution in the LA direction, that makes direct 3D approaches extremely involved. In addition, the delineation of cardiac structures and the tracking of adequate trajectories of material points are coupled problems; thus the segmentations have to account (and may even benefit from the fact) that the heart is not a static structure.

1.1.1. First approaches

Cardiac segmentation has been an active area of research since the early nineties. At that time, segmentation techniques were usually general purpose methods (Clarke et al., 1995) applied to the cardiac case. Some references of interest are Gosh-tasby and Turner (1995); Nachtomy et al. (1998); Waiter et al. (1999), which constitute good entry points into the cardiac segmentation problem. In these techniques, some sort of manual intervention is needed to let the algorithm start or to guide it through the segmentation process. Generally, they process a subset of the 4D dataset and the analysis is extended to the whole set.

1.1.2. 2D techniques

More recent methods, fostered by improved hardware computational capabilities, have dealt with the integration of regional intensity and gradient information with anatomical and functional properties of the cardiac structures. That is the case of snakes or AC methods (Kass et al., 1988) and level set procedures (Malladi et al., 1995), which have been applied by many authors to the segmentation of the cardiac structures.

Specifically, in Avedisjan et al. (1999); Hautvast et al. (2006) AC are propagated in time for a complete segmentation of several structures (including the myocardium) throughout the cardiac cycle. The propagated contours are completely defined by the user. In addition, each slice in the volume is processed separately. Besides this, in Hautvast et al. (2006) a set of segmented images is required in order to estimate the parameters of the method, which is carried out by factor analysis, so it can be considered a supervised approach. An approach based on level sets is presented in Paragios (2002). The evolution of the myocardium contours is coupled by favoring the solutions that maintain the distance between the contours constant and inside a predefined range. User interaction is also needed in this approach and continuity is not guaranteed in the LA direction (2D + T method). In Schaerer et al. (2010) an AC model is developed which is inspired by the biomechanical properties of the myocardial muscle and able to consider the temporal smoothness and periodicity of cardiac motion. Despite the good theoretical properties of the method, reported results are only moderately successful. This is likely to be due to the known limitation of most AC and level set based methods, which are very sensitive to noise and initialization due to their edge-based nature. Limitations of most of the foregoing methods have been alleviated in Corsi et al. (2006); Fradkin et al. (2008); Paragios (2002); Pluempitiwiriyawej et al. (2005) by means of geodesic regions. In Pluempitiwiriyawej et al. (2005) a 2D + T stochastic level set scheme is presented which combines a prior shape model with both edge and region-based information. The method proceeds hierarchically: first, it segments the heart and then it distinguishes the muscle from the cavities. One outstanding feature of this method is the dynamic adaptation of the energy functional being optimized. At the beginning of the optimization process, edge and texture models are the main drivers of the segmentation, with shape priors becoming more relevant approaching the end. However, this feature is implemented heuristically and, probably of greater

relevance, it is not adapted to the different nature of each of the images analyzed.

1.1.3. 3D techniques

Frangi et al. (2001) showed the relevance of the approaches based on deformable models for myocardial segmentation. Under the deformable model paradigm, one can include a set of techniques that integrate the 3D extension of AC (active surfaces) with prior knowledge about shape and/or appearance of the object to segment. A large number of geometric and physical representations have been applied for cardiac modeling, including those based on 3D level sets, as pointed out in Lynch et al. (2008); Paragios (2002). ASM (van Assen et al., 2006, 2008; Frangi et al., 2002; Koikkalainen et al., 2008; Zhu et al., 2010) and AAM (Andreopoulos and Tsotsos, 2008; van der Geest et al., 1997; Mitchell et al., 2002; Peters et al., 2010; Stegmann and Pedersen, 2005; Zhang et al., 2010) deserve special attention under this paradigm since they are part of an emerging trend in the segmentation of medical images. ASM are built upon a priori shape knowledge usually extracted from an atlas created from a training set of images. AAM are similar to ASM, but they include additional information on the object intensity which leads to a combined shape-appearance statistical analysis. Although training-based methods may suffer from overfitting if the training set does not properly represent the test set (when, for instance, healthy subjects are used for training and patients for testing), they allow for the inclusion of anatomical or functional problem-specific knowledge in the segmentation. Finally, Shang et al. (2006) introduces a method which combines the robustness of Gradient Vector Flow formulation of AC with a hierarchical statistical shape model and segmentation procedure for the myocardium.

Although deformable models may be elegant solutions for dealing with the relationship between endocardium and epicardium surfaces, some approaches based on them have ignored the temporal dimension analysis (Kaus et al., 2004; Lötjönen et al., 2004; Zhuang et al., 2010) and others have resorted to a parametric representation of it (Bardinet et al., 1996; Lynch et al., 2008). Sometimes the temporal segmentation is performed sequentially, with the output of the previous phase being the initial guess for the current one (Hautvast et al., 2006; Zhu et al., 2010). However, this idea may lead to a lack of coherence at the end of the sequence due to the periodic motion of the heart. In Lorenzo-Valdés et al. (2004) prior temporal and spatial cardiac information is obtained from a probabilistic atlas of healthy volunteers. In addition, the segmentation algorithm incorporates temporal and spatial contextual information by means of a 4D MRF of tissue labels of the image pixels. The parameters of the field are first estimated on a supervised basis. Then an EM algorithm is used for the simultaneous unsupervised parameter estimation and optimization of the field (something similar is implemented in Lynch et al. (2008), but in this case applied only to the temporal evolution of the surfaces). Their results reflect the robust and flexible behavior of the method although a global connectivity filter is required to guarantee the consistency of the detected regions. Though validated for SPECT images and with parameters tuned manually,

an unsupervised 4D segmentation algorithm based on a simplex mesh surface is presented in Montagnat and Delingette (2005). The model includes temporal periodicity of the surface, constraints the point trajectories to follow a path closely related to their reference path and favors the smoothness of the deformation evolution by adopting motion governing laws.

1.1.4. Other approaches

Not all the cardiac segmentation approaches are restricted to the deformable model paradigm. Pednekar et al. (2006) propose an automatic approach for myocardial segmentation based on different techniques. The LV is first automatically located using a motion map and the Hough transform and then it is extended with fuzzy techniques throughout the volume by using continuity and intensity coherence restrictions. Finally, the cardiac cavity is segmented by the optimization of a cost function that incorporates smoothness restrictions, intensity and gradient information. This work is extended in Kurkure et al. (2009), where the localization is based on the information of LA images and the fuzzy techniques are refined. The approach proposed in Lynch et al. (2006) also performs an automatic location of the LV cavity. After a preprocessing step that includes pre-filtering and intensity-based clustering, the LV cavity is located by shape and intensity criteria. Then, the epicardium is segmented by means of edge information with restrictions about the conservation of the MT and forcing the continuity of the border. The work in Lu et al. (2009) automatically detects the LV cavity by using a roundness measure and performs the segmentation in polar coordinates. For the endocardium it uses an Otsu threshold procedure (Otsu, 1979) together with some morphological operations whereas for the epicardium it uses a region growing procedure and morphological refinements. Both contours are smoothed by truncating their respective Fourier descriptors. Another approach is proposed in Cousty et al. (2010), where a method based on discrete mathematical morphology is used to segment the endocardium and the epicardium separately. The method considers the 4D structure of the data and offers good results in practice, but the parameters involved largely depend on the acquisition protocol. Finally, in Lee et al. (2010), region growing and AC-based techniques are used respectively for the endocardial and epicardial segmentation. This work reports satisfactory results in terms of both the epi and endocardial volumes at ED as well as of the MM throughout the cardiac cycle. The method, however, requires manual intervention (according to the authors, much less than in a customarily-used commercial software) and temporal regularization is not considered.

1.2. Precedents of the work

The segmentation methodology has some of its foundations in previous contributions of the authors (Martin and Alberola, 2002; Martín-Fernández and Alberola-López, 2005; Martín-Fernández et al., 2007). It is interesting to pay attention to some previous proposals somewhat related to this method although they are applied to different imaging modalities.

As Storvik (1994) pointed out, the use of energy functionals in deformable models falls into the Bayesian framework. The

energy of a deformable model consists in the superposition of internal and external forces that serve respectively to introduce smoothness constraints and to guide the model to relevant image features. The minimization of such energy functional corresponds to the MAP estimator in the space of states of the model, although other criteria for estimation are also possible. In many cases the dimensionality and the highly non linear nature of the problem imply that it is impossible to find this optimal solution directly, so iterative algorithms are used to make an initial state of the model evolve dynamically to the optimal solution. Unlike in the Bayesian MRF-based approach, in the conventional deformable model paradigm it is sometimes difficult to escape from local minima or to control the dynamics of the iterative method. Moreover, the stochastic approach allows to estimate the optimal weights of each of the potential terms in which the energy is decomposed and hence to improve the adaptability of designed algorithms. Finally, measures of uncertainty in the solutions can be established naturally in this formulation.

The precedents of our work have been developed in the field of echocardiography (Dias and Leitão, 1996; Friedland and Adam, 1989; Haas et al., 2000; Mignotte et al., 2001) and angiography (de Figueiredo and Leitão, 1992), but, surprisingly, and to the best of our knowledge, no attempts of applying this segmentation framework to cardiac MRI have been reported. This could be in part due to the fact that this modality presents clearer information content, so the smoothing restrictions of the aforementioned methods may seem unnecessary. Nevertheless, the high dimensionality of the problem and the need of integration of a priori knowledge in the most pathological or rare cases, could further support the opposite argument. In the present work, we try to shed some light on this question. Besides this, we try to assess the feasibility of adopting a direct 4D approach inside the Markovian deformable model paradigm, which is also a novel contribution of the method.

We have developed an automated and unsupervised segmentation method for the myocardium in SA cine MRI. The segmentation task is modeled as an optimization problem in which the optimal time-varying surface is obtained in a discrete space of locations. The method also integrates smoothness, image intensity and gradient related features in an optimal way under a MRF framework by ML parameter estimation. It presents several advantages when compared to current state-of-the-art methods by combining the following issues: first, as a coupled 3D + T model, it provides smoothness in the temporal direction in a way that considers the cyclical nature of this component and couples the myocardium contours in a simple but powerful way. Second, problems related to overfitting are avoided, since it provides a completely unsupervised segmentation algorithm. Finally, when the energy to be optimized is build upon a set of terms that account for different elements that influence the problem, some authors have obtained better results by a gradual adjustment of the relative weight of each term through the algorithm evolution (Montagnat and Delingette, 2005; Pluempitiwiriyaewej et al., 2005). Our method naturally performs this adjustment since it incorporates all the inferential capabilities of the Bayesian framework.

The paper is structured as follows: Section 2 gives an over-

all description of the algorithm. Section 3 presents the model components and parametrization together with its formulation as a MRF. A description of the potential terms, parameter estimation and optimization of the field is included in Section 4. The parameters involved in the method as well as some other implementation issues are summarized in Section 5 for helping further reproducibility. In Section 6 the method proposed is validated and characterized in terms of the calculation of cardiac functional parameters and regional distances between manual and automatic surfaces. Insight into the diagnostic capability and the stochastic parameter estimation relevance is also provided. A study of the complexity of the algorithm along with its main advantages, limitations and potential usefulness are summarized in Section 7 to end up with some conclusions in Section 8. The initial model fitting method is described in Appendix A and Appendix B compiles exhaustively the notation used in the paper.

2. Overview of the method

This Section is intended to clarify the algorithmic flux of the method. The overall procedure is presented in Fig. 1. The input of the algorithm is the 4D cardiac image (in blue). The output is the segmentation of the myocardium (in red). The main steps can be summarized as:

- **Myocardium detection.**

- **CC detection:** The objective of this step is to roughly localize the CC to confine the analysis of the image to the relevant structures.
- **CC tissue modeling:** The objective is to model the characteristic tissues for the CC; namely, air, muscle and blood. To that end a FGMM is used.
- **LV detection:** The objective is to obtain an estimation of the center and coarse estimations of the radii of an annulus that fits the myocardium for each SA slice.
- **LV tissue modeling:** It is analogous to the CC tissue modeling stage, but in this case the objective is to model the characteristic tissues in the surroundings of the LV.

- **MRF segmentation.**

- **Image likelihood modeling:** The objective is to model the likelihood distribution used in the MRF. For that purpose, the intensity and gradient of the original image are sampled in the different regions and boundaries obtained in the LV tissue modeling.
- **MRF modeling:** Its main steps are:
 - * Build a 3D grid in the angular, temporal and LA directions.
 - * Define a MRF of SA radii over that grid (that includes both the prior and the likelihood terms).

Figure 1: Block diagram of the algorithm.

- * Compute the intensity and gradient likelihood over different image subsets build upon the previous grid and radii.
- **Optimization:** It is implemented by the recursive simulation and estimation of the parameters of the MRF, which integrates smoothness restrictions for the myocardium boundaries along each direction of the grid together with the likelihood terms.

Appendix A describes in detail the myocardium detection procedure with a deeper insight on each step and with graphical examples whereas the next two Sections describe the MRF based segmentation, which constitutes the core of the paper.

3. MRF formulation

In this Section we present the stochastic formulation of the myocardium segmentation, introduce the notation and summarize some background theory on MRFs. We are given a discrete 4D cardiac image \mathbf{I} , which consist of the set of values $I[\mathbf{b}]$, where $\mathbf{b} = [m, n, p, q]$ addresses its pixels, with m representing the SA rows, n the SA columns, p a given SA image and q a cardiac phase. Taking into consideration the annular structure of the myocardium in the SA views, once given its center \mathbf{C} , a convenient way to represent the information in the surroundings of the LV is by using polar coordinates of the form (r, ψ) . This system can be extended in the LA axis by the insertion of a new coordinate z and allowing the center of the polar system to vary along the LA axis, so $\mathbf{C} = \mathbf{C}(z)$. This extension deals with the anisotropy in the resolution of the LA axis with respect to the SA axes and gives room to handle motion artifacts between different SA slices due to the fact that breathing motion reveals itself as a rigid transformation of the image coordinates. Finally, considering the cyclical nature of the cardiac motion, the temporal dimension can be encoded in a periodic coordinate ϕ ¹. In this coordinate system the myocardium can be defined as the region enclosed between two radial functions $r^1(\psi, z, \phi)$ and $r^2(\psi, z, \phi)$ restricted by $0 < r^1 < r^2$, which correspond respectively to the endocardial and epicardial boundaries. This way, the problem of myocardial segmentation becomes the estimation of the two aforementioned functions in the space given by

¹This is the case provided that the acquisition of the cardiac phases covers the entire cardiac cycle (the case of retrospective gating) or, at least, the systole and a part of the diastole, since motion at late diastole is usually small (the case of prospective gating).

the (ψ, z, ϕ) coordinates. This space can be discretized and consequently represented by a collection of indices $[j, p, q]$, where $j \in \mathcal{J}$ denotes a SA ray traced from the origin of the coordinate system $\mathbf{C}[p]$ and in the SA plane, with $p \in \mathcal{P}$ and $q \in \mathcal{Q}$ indexing SA images and cardiac phases respectively. The rays are uniformly distributed, so $\psi_j = \frac{j}{2\pi|\mathcal{J}|}$. The estimation of the radial functions can also be converted to a discrete problem by the quantization of the radial variable into a set of indices k . This way, in the discrete formulation, the problem of myocardial segmentation is now posed as the estimation of two discrete quantized functions $r_{k^1}[j, p, q]$ and $r_{k^2}[j, p, q]$ subject to

$$0 < r_{k^1} < r_{k^2} < r_{\max}, \quad (1)$$

where $k^i \in \mathcal{K} = \{1, \dots, \mathcal{K}\}$ for $i \in \{1, 2\}$ such that

$$r_{k^i} = \frac{(k^i - 0.5)r_{\max}}{|\mathcal{K}|}. \quad (2)$$

The estimation of the radial functions can be accomplished within a stochastic framework. The idea is to define a MRF over the set of *sites* $\mathbf{s} \in \mathcal{S}$ given by $\mathbf{s} = [j, p, q]$. For every site, we have a discrete random variable $\mathbf{K}_s \in \mathcal{K}'$ that takes on values in the pair of radii indexed by $[k^1; k^2]$. Considering the restrictions in (1), the cardinality of this set is $|\mathcal{K}'| = |\mathcal{K}|(|\mathcal{K}| - 1)/2$. The product space $\Omega = \mathcal{K}'^{\mathcal{S}}$ represents the space of configurations of the random array $\mathbf{K} = [\mathbf{K}_1, \dots, \mathbf{K}_{|\mathcal{S}|}]$. This way, given a realization of the array $\mathbf{K} = \mathbf{k} = [\mathbf{k}^1; \mathbf{k}^2]$, we have that $\mathbf{k} \in \Omega$. With the restriction $\Pi(\mathbf{k}) > 0$, this set of random variables forms a random field. The MRF is built from the definition of a system of contextual dependencies over the geometry of the sites. These dependencies are encoded in the form of a *neighborhood system* $\delta(\mathbf{s})$. A customary way to define the neighborhood system is by means of the order of the neighborhood, which is the smallest integer that satisfies $c \geq \|\mathbf{s} - \mathbf{s}'\|^2$, where $\mathbf{s}' \in \delta(\mathbf{s})$.

The Hammersley-Clifford theorem (Winkler, 1995) states that if a Random Field is a MRF for the neighborhood δ , it is also a Gibbs Random Field for that neighborhood and vice versa. In a Gibbs Random Field we have the relationship

$$\Pi(\mathbf{k}) = \frac{1}{Z} \exp\left(-\sum_{\mathbf{c} \in \mathcal{C}} V_{\mathbf{c}}(\mathbf{k})\right). \quad (3)$$

(3) models the probability of occurrence of a realization of the field as an exponential addition of potential terms normalized by Z , the so-called *partition function*. \mathcal{C} represents a clique

Figure 2: MRF model for a given SA image. The set of rays ψ_j appears in green. In red the possible radii r_k . In blue a configuration for the endocardium \mathbf{k}^1 and in yellow a configuration for the epicardium \mathbf{k}^2 .

induced by δ and C represents the set of cliques induced by δ (Paget and Longstaff, 1997). V are potential functions, which take the form $V_C(\mathbf{k}) = \nu_C U_C(\mathbf{k})$. The parameters $\nu = \nu_C$, $C \in C$ are the parameters of the field, which can be estimated or manually tuned, whereas $\mathbf{U} = U_C$ are the normalized potentials.

From a Bayesian perspective, given the image data \mathbf{I} , one may consider the field

$$\Pi(\mathbf{k} | \mathbf{I}) \propto \Pi(\mathbf{k})f(\mathbf{I} | \mathbf{k}). \quad (4)$$

which is also Markovian and where $f(\mathbf{I} | \mathbf{k})$ is known as the likelihood function of the data given a configuration of the field².

Therefore, the segmentation problem is modeled as a 3D MRF of radii. This MRF is cyclical in its first and third components. The neighborhood system is of order $c = 4$ as it encodes smoothing terms based on finite differences up to order two. The field is homogeneous in the sense that the parameters of the potential terms ν are the same for all sites, and anisotropic, as they differ for the different variables of the grid of sites, $[j, p, q]$. A schematic representation of the space of configurations and a realization of the field for a given SA image is depicted in Fig. 2.

4. Design and optimization of the field

Whereas Section 3 presents the general framework of segmentation, the purpose of this current Section is to gain deeper insight into the model by specifying the design adopted for the prior $\Pi(\mathbf{k})$ and the likelihood $f(\mathbf{I} | \mathbf{k})$ as well as the criteria to carry out inferences on $\Pi(\mathbf{k} | \mathbf{I})$.

²Although the image data are discrete, the assumption of a continuous probability density function has to do with the likelihood model we have developed, which assume continuous distributions (see Section 4.2.1).

4.1. Prior terms

The purpose of these terms is to impose a certain degree of smoothness on the segmentation solution. This is implemented as favoring those configurations that keep the first and second order differential area derivatives close to zero for each element relevant in the segmentation problem; that is, the SA radii and the MT. The discretization of these derivatives is carried out by means of first and second order finite differences. We denote $\mathbf{a} = (a_1, a_2, a_3) = (\psi, z, \phi)$ and $\mathbf{s}_1 = [1, 0, 0]$, $\mathbf{s}_2 = [0, 1, 0]$, $\mathbf{s}_3 = [0, 0, 1]$. Besides this, we define the MT function as $r^3 = r^2 - r^1$ and perform the following approximations:

$$\left| \frac{\partial(r^j)^2}{\partial a_u} \right|_{\mathbf{a}_0} \simeq |(r_{\mathbf{s}_0}^j)^2 - (r_{\mathbf{s}_0+\mathbf{s}_u}^j)^2|, \quad 1 \leq u \leq 3 \quad (5)$$

$$\left| \frac{\partial^2(r^j)^2}{\partial a_u^2} \right|_{\mathbf{a}_0} \simeq |(r_{\mathbf{s}_0}^j)^2 - 2(r_{\mathbf{s}_0+\mathbf{s}_u}^j)^2 + (r_{\mathbf{s}_0+2\mathbf{s}_u}^j)^2|, \quad (6)$$

$$1 \leq u \leq 3$$

$$\left| \frac{\partial^2(r^i)^2}{\partial a_u \partial a_v} \right|_{\mathbf{a}_0} \simeq |(r_{\mathbf{s}_0}^i)^2 - (r_{\mathbf{s}_0+\mathbf{s}_u}^i)^2 - (r_{\mathbf{s}_0+\mathbf{s}_v}^i)^2 + (r_{\mathbf{s}_0+\mathbf{s}_u+\mathbf{s}_v}^i)^2|, \quad 1 \leq u < v \leq 3, \quad (7)$$

with $1 \leq i \leq 3$, respectively for the endocardial radius, the epicardial radius and the MT, \mathbf{s}_0 denoting the closest grid point to \mathbf{a}_0 and $r_{\mathbf{s}_0}^i$ is the radius function for surface i at that grid point.

This way, the model favors those solutions that maintain the areas of the endocardium, epicardium and myocardium constant or progressing linearly between neighboring sites. With these assumptions, all the potentials are constructed by means of 2-element cliques for the first order difference, 3-element cliques for the second order one and 4-element cliques for the approximation of the cross derivative, so in (3) we have that $C = \{C_2^{ui}, C_3^{ui}, C_4^{uvi}\}$. This is implemented in the MRF by means of the normalized potentials:

$$V_{C_2^{ui}}(\mathbf{k}) = \nu_{C_2^{ui}} \sum_{\mathbf{s}} |(r_{\mathbf{s}}^i)^2 - (r_{\mathbf{s}+\mathbf{s}_u}^i)^2| \quad (8)$$

$$V_{C_3^{ui}}(\mathbf{k}) = \nu_{C_3^{ui}} \sum_{\mathbf{s}} |(r_{\mathbf{s}}^i)^2 - 2(r_{\mathbf{s}+\mathbf{s}_u}^i)^2 + (r_{\mathbf{s}+2\mathbf{s}_u}^i)^2| \quad (9)$$

$$V_{C_4^{uvi}}(\mathbf{k}) = \nu_{C_4^{uvi}} \sum_{\mathbf{s}} |(r_{\mathbf{s}}^i)^2 - (r_{\mathbf{s}+\mathbf{s}_u}^i)^2 - (r_{\mathbf{s}+\mathbf{s}_v}^i)^2 + (r_{\mathbf{s}+\mathbf{s}_u+\mathbf{s}_v}^i)^2|, \quad (10)$$

with r and k related by (2). Note the fact that the parameters of the field perform a relative scaling of the different potential terms; this is the reason why the spacing between grid points was not included in the finite difference approximations of (5), (6) and (7). This scheme is expected to help in the difficult problem of epicardial surface extraction. Moreover, the spatial smoothness constraints should be able to exclude the papillary muscles from the myocardium. Finally, the temporal smoothness is expected to maintain the temporal coherence of the result³.

³The basic idea for the temporal derivative is that in the systolic and early

4.2. Likelihood terms

This Section describes the likelihood model of the field together with the procedure used to estimate the parameters of the likelihood terms.

4.2.1. Likelihood model

The likelihood of the image given a myocardium segmentation $f(\mathbf{I} | \mathbf{k})$ is difficult to model. To achieve the goal of designing a model that is both realistic and mathematically tractable, our implementation retains some of the main features that the image shows in the surroundings of the myocardial region and simultaneously aims at simplifying the complexity of the overall distribution. The main features considered are the following:

- **Intensity of pixels inside the myocardium.** It guides the segmentation result to enclose a region with an intensity close to the one assumed for the myocardium.
- **Intensity of pixels at the boundary of the myocardium.** The boundary of the myocardium is usually blurred due to the PVE (Santago and Gage, 1995). Two main cases arise: the transition between muscle and air and the transition between muscle and blood. The model expects these two cases as indicated below.
- **Gradient modulus of pixels inside the myocardium.** It avoids abrupt intensity changes inside the segmented region, which is consistent with the fact that the myocardium presents a homogeneous intensity pattern.
- **Gradient modulus of pixels at the boundary of the myocardium.** The gradient also exhibits different values in the transition between muscle and air and the transition between muscle and blood. As in the first case intensity values are closer to each other, gradients are generally lower.

These four terms are modelled by their respective distributions $f_{wy}(\mathbf{D}_w | \mathbf{k})$, with $w = \{1, 2\}$ and $y = \{1, 2\}$, where $\mathbf{D}_1 = \mathbf{I}$ and $\mathbf{D}_2 = |\nabla \mathbf{I}|$. This way, w addresses an image feature (i.e., intensity and gradient⁴) and y is an index to a myocardium zone (i. e., region and boundary).

In order to simplify the joint distribution, some assumptions are made:

1. Conditional independence among the likelihood terms:

$$f(\mathbf{I} | \mathbf{k}) = \prod_{wy} f_{wy}(\mathbf{D}_w | \mathbf{k}). \quad (11)$$

2. Conditional independence among the MRF variables:

$$f_{wy}(\mathbf{D}_w | \mathbf{k}) = \prod_{\mathbf{s}} f_{wy}(\mathbf{D}_w | \mathbf{k}_{\mathbf{s}}). \quad (12)$$

diastolic phases it progresses linearly and in the late diastolic phase it remains constant. The parameter estimation is expected to balance both contributions appropriately. It is likely that allowing the corresponding parameters of the field to vary temporally would provide more precise results. Nevertheless, for the sake of simplicity, temporal inhomogeneity has not been considered.

⁴In our implementation this gradient is computed only in the SA plane directions, to prevent from inconsistencies caused by the misalignment between slices due to patient breathing.

Figure 3: Subsets ε and γ for a given SA MRI image of the heart. Note that ε (in cyan) does not depend on the particular configuration $\mathbf{k}_{\mathbf{s}}$ and that γ_2^1 (in blue) gathers information related to the endocardial boundary, γ_2^2 (in yellow) information of the epicardial boundary and γ_1 (in magenta) regional myocardial information.

3. Local information extraction (Martín-Fernández and Alberola-López, 2005):

$$f_{wy}(\mathbf{D}_w | \mathbf{k}_{\mathbf{s}}) = f_{wy}(\mathbf{D}_w[\gamma_y[\mathbf{k}_{\mathbf{s}}]]). \quad (13)$$

The subsets γ_y correspond to the zones from which the likelihood information is extracted and depend on the myocardial segmentation results for a given MRF site. An auxiliary subset is used in their definition $\varepsilon[\mathbf{s}] = \{\mathbf{b} : |\angle([m, n]_{C[p]} - \psi_j) < \pi/|\mathcal{J}|\}$, where $\angle([m, n]_{C[p]})$ represents the orientation of the pixel location. This subset, for a given slice and cardiac phase, comprises the pixels whose closest ray is the one indexed by j . Then, the subset boundaries in the radial direction are defined as:

$$\begin{aligned} \gamma_1[\mathbf{k}_{\mathbf{s}}] &= \{\mathbf{b} \in \varepsilon[\mathbf{s}] : r_s^1 \leq \|[m, n]\|_{C[p]} \leq r_s^2\}, \\ \gamma_2[\mathbf{k}_{\mathbf{s}}] &= \bigcup_i \gamma_2^i[k_s^i], \\ \gamma_2^i[k_s^i] &= \left\{ \mathbf{b} \in \varepsilon[\mathbf{s}] : \|[m, n]\|_{C[p]} - r_s^i \leq \frac{r_{max}}{2|\mathcal{K}|} \right\}, \end{aligned} \quad (14)$$

again with r and k related by (2) and $\|[m, n]\|_{C[p]}$ denoting the radius of the pixel location. These subsets include the pixels of the image corresponding to the myocardial region ($y = 1$) and myocardial boundaries ($y = 2$) for a given configuration in a site of the field. The myocardial region corresponds, for a given ray, slice, and cardiac phase, to those pixels whose radius is between the radii indexed by k^1 and k^2 , whereas myocardial boundaries correspond to those which closest radius is the one indexed by k^i . These subsets are represented in Fig. 3.

4. Conditional independence between the endocardial and

epicardial boundary distributions:

$$f_{w2}(\mathbf{D}_w[\gamma_2]) = \prod_i f_{w2}^i(\mathbf{D}_w[\gamma_2^i]). \quad (15)$$

5. Conditional independence among the pixels that conform the subsets and normalization by the subset size:

$$\begin{aligned} f_{w1}(\mathbf{D}_w[\gamma_1]) &= \exp\left(\frac{1}{|\gamma_1|} \sum_{\mathbf{b} \in \gamma_1} \log(f_{w1}(D_w[\mathbf{b}]))\right) \\ f_{w2}^i(\mathbf{D}_w[\gamma_2^i]) &= \exp\left(\frac{1}{|\gamma_2^i|} \sum_{\mathbf{b} \in \gamma_2^i} \log(f_{w2}^i(D_w[\mathbf{b}]))\right) \end{aligned} \quad (16)$$

The right-hand side in (16) is the exponential addition of the normalized log-likelihood of the pixel intensities or gradients, which are supposed to be identically distributed for each pixel. The distributions associated with each term have been selected according to the following ideas:

- The intensity of the pixels inside the myocardium is assumed to be homogeneous and modeled by a Gaussian distribution. This statistical model has been used extensively for tissue modeling in MRI (Lorenzo-Valdés et al., 2004; Zhu et al., 2010):

$$f_{11}(x) = g(x) = \frac{1}{\sigma \sqrt{2\pi}} \exp\left(-\frac{(x - \mu)^2}{2\sigma^2}\right). \quad (17)$$

- The intensity of the pixels at the boundary of the myocardium is built upon the conditional probability given the type of transition of the pixel (i. e., muscle to blood and muscle to air), denoted as d . It is modeled also by means of a Gaussian distribution. Though this distribution is not fully justified in this case, some references have pointed out its feasibility (Ruan et al., 2000). The transition for the endocardial boundary is always between blood and muscle (except for the papillary muscles, whose presence is meant to be avoided by the regularization terms of the field, as pointed in Section 4.1), whereas both possibilities can take place for the epicardial boundary, so we consider a binary random variable to model the transition T which can take on the values MB and MA and write:

$$\begin{aligned} f_{12}^1(x) &= g_1(x) \\ f_{12}^2(x) &= g_1(x | \text{MB})\Pi(\text{MB}) + g_2(x | \text{MA})\Pi(\text{MA}), \\ g_d(x) &= \frac{1}{\sigma_d \sqrt{2\pi}} \exp\left(-\frac{(x - \mu_d)^2}{2\sigma_d^2}\right), \quad d = \{1, 2\}, \end{aligned} \quad (18)$$

as in the endocardial case $T = \text{MB}$. For simplicity, the transition law has the following form for the pixels affecting the epicardium:

$$\begin{aligned} T = \text{MB} &\iff \cos(\angle(\nabla \mathbf{I}), \angle([m, n]_{\mathbf{C}_p})) \geq 0 \\ T = \text{MA} &\iff \cos(\angle(\nabla \mathbf{I}), \angle([m, n]_{\mathbf{C}_p})) < 0, \end{aligned} \quad (19)$$

so the radial changes from darker to brighter in the intensity are considered transitions between muscle and blood

and changes from brighter to darker are transitions between muscle and air. Hence, in our implementation a hard decision is made according to (19) so only the chosen component is used in (18) but not the mixture.

Modelling intensity terms at the boundaries gives the field the possibility of not favoring gradients coming from edges at intensity levels different from those expected.

- The gradient modulus of the pixels inside the myocardium is assumed to be homogeneous and modeled by an Exponential distribution so the likelihood decreases with increasing gradient:

$$f_{21}(x) = e(x) = \lambda \exp(-\lambda x). \quad (20)$$

- The gradient modulus of the pixels at the boundary of the myocardium is modeled analogously to the intensity of pixels at the boundary of the myocardium by using a conditional probability given the type of transition of the pixel, as given by (19). A Gamma distribution is used for each type of transition, which has given good empirical results as compared with Gaussian, LogGaussian or Wald distributions:

$$\begin{aligned} f_{22}^1(x) &= h_1(x) \\ f_{22}^2(x) &= h_1(x | \text{MB})\Pi(\text{MB}) + h_2(x | \text{MA})\Pi(\text{MA}), \\ h_d(x) &= \frac{x^{\kappa_d - 1}}{\theta_d^{\kappa_d} \Gamma(\kappa_d)} \exp\left(-\frac{x}{\theta_d}\right), \quad d = \{1, 2\}. \end{aligned} \quad (21)$$

4.2.2. Parameter estimation of the likelihood terms

The estimation of the parameters of the likelihood terms of the MRF makes use of a labeled image of the LV surroundings. In our case this labeling comes from the ML tissue estimation given the parameters of the FGMM obtained by the EM algorithm, as anticipated in Section 2 and further developed in Appendix A.4. Nevertheless, more sophisticated methods are possible for the labeling which could further improve the performance of the algorithm. Anyway, the final segmentation results have proven to be robust with respect to small labeling errors, so no further attention has been paid to other methods. It is interesting to note that, with this assumption, our method incorporates application specific geometric and dynamic restrictions to a generic labeling of the image data in order to obtain the final segmentation of an object of interest.

Different masks are extracted from the labeled image to obtain a set of pixels that make up the sample from which the parameters of the distributions in (17), (18), (20) and (21) are estimated. Let \mathbf{M}_{w2}^d be the set of sampling mask images for the boundary case and \mathbf{M}_{w1} the set for the regional case, according to the likelihood terms defined in Section 4.2.1, so w indexes an image feature and d a transition type. The labeled image is denoted by \mathbf{L} and takes on values in the set $0 \leq l \leq 3$, corresponding respectively to background, air, muscle and blood. Let \mathbf{L}_l denote the image given by $L_l[\mathbf{b}] = 1$ if $L[\mathbf{b}] = l$ and

$L_l[\mathbf{b}] = 0$ otherwise. Then:

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathbf{M}_{11} &= \{\mathbf{b} : \mathbf{L}_2[\mathbf{b}] = 1 \cup |\nabla \mathbf{L}_2[\mathbf{b}]| \neq 0\} \\
\mathbf{M}_{21} &= \{\mathbf{b} : \mathbf{L}_2[\mathbf{b}] = 1 \cap |\nabla \mathbf{L}_2[\mathbf{b}]| = 0\} \\
\mathbf{M}_{w_2}^1 &= \{\mathbf{b} : |\nabla \mathbf{L}_2[\mathbf{b}]| \neq 0 \cap |\nabla \mathbf{L}_3[\mathbf{b}]| \neq 0\} \\
\mathbf{M}_{w_2}^2 &= \{\mathbf{b} : |\nabla \mathbf{L}_2[\mathbf{b}]| \neq 0 \cap |\nabla \mathbf{L}_1[\mathbf{b}]| \neq 0\}.
\end{aligned} \tag{22}$$

An example of these sets is presented in Fig. 4 together with the labeling \mathbf{L} . The sample for the estimation of the parameters of the regional intensity term in Fig. 4(b) is built upon the region corresponding to that term plus its boundaries. The range of intensities is thus unbounded due to the fact that the labeling contains a thin region surrounding the pixels labelled as muscle. The sample for the estimation of the regional gradient term in Fig. 4(c) excludes the boundaries of the region to avoid sampling pixels with large gradient. The sample for the estimation of the boundary terms is the same for intensity and gradient, but it differentiates between the boundaries of the myocardium with blood-labeled regions –Fig. 4(d)– and with air-labeled regions –Fig. 4(e). The ML estimator is used to obtain the parameters of the likelihood functions by sampling the respective feature (i.e. intensity and gradient modulus) over these sets.

4.3. Parameter estimation and optimization of the field

The segmentation solution is stated as the MPM configuration of the posterior field,

$$\mathbf{k}_s^* = \underset{\mathbf{k}_s}{\operatorname{argmax}} \Pi(\mathbf{k}_s | \mathbf{I}; \boldsymbol{\nu}) \tag{23}$$

The criterion behind the MPM optimization is to minimize the number of misclassified sites of the field so it is suitable for segmentation. Though the Iterated Conditional Modes and the Simulated Annealing optimization methods were also explored, the MPM is the adopted optimization scheme mainly because it can be naturally derived from sampling the posterior distribution, which is a basic ingredient in the parameter estimation procedure described hereafter. Accordingly, our implementation uses the GSA to obtain the MPM configuration of the field (Winkler, 1995).

The main problem for the estimation of the parameter vector $\boldsymbol{\nu}$ is that it is coupled with the segmentation solution. A ML parameter estimator has been introduced in Younes (1989) to handle this combined optimization-estimation problem optimally. The key idea is to perform statistical inference from the observed image \mathbf{I} with the aid of the model for the field \mathbf{k} . The equation to be solved is:

$$\boldsymbol{\nu}^* = \underset{\boldsymbol{\nu}}{\operatorname{argmax}} f(\mathbf{I}; \boldsymbol{\nu}). \tag{24}$$

After some manipulations (Winkler, 1995), one gets the derivatives of the log-likelihood of \mathbf{I} which are given by:

$$\nabla \log(f(\mathbf{I}; \boldsymbol{\nu})) = \mathbb{E}[\mathbf{U}; \boldsymbol{\nu}] - \mathbb{E}[\mathbf{U} | \mathbf{I}; \boldsymbol{\nu}]. \tag{25}$$

In order to obtain the ML solution, one has to equal (25) to zero, which has no closed form, so an iterative procedure has to be

Figure 5: Model based MRF segmentation.

implemented. On the basis of a stochastic gradient algorithm, the parameter vector is updated at each iteration by computing the derivatives of the log-likelihood from the simulation of two fields \mathbf{K}_1 and \mathbf{K}_2 that follow the laws $\Pi(\mathbf{k}; \boldsymbol{\nu})$ and $\Pi(\mathbf{k} | \mathbf{I}; \boldsymbol{\nu})$. The simulation serves to approximate the expectations in (25) and is implemented by the GSA. The updating rule is:

$$\begin{aligned}
\boldsymbol{\nu}_{t+1} - \boldsymbol{\nu}_t &= \frac{1}{(t + t_0)B} \sum_{t'=0}^{T_{\text{EXP}}-1} \mathbf{U}(\mathbf{K}_{1,t+1-t'}; \boldsymbol{\nu}_{t-t'}) \\
&\quad - \frac{1}{(t + t_0)B} \sum_{t'=0}^{T_{\text{EXP}}-1} \mathbf{U}(\mathbf{K}_{2,t+1-t'}; \boldsymbol{\nu}_{t-t'})
\end{aligned} \tag{26}$$

where B and t_0 are constants to ensure convergence and T_{EXP} is the number of simulated samples to approximate the expectations.

Fig. 5 represents a block diagram of the combined simulation-estimation approach. The MRF is built on the basis of the image under analysis, a labeling of the tissues that comprise the myocardium and its surroundings, \mathbf{L} , and the center of the LV for each SA image, $\mathbf{C}[p]$. Then the algorithm iterates between the simulation of the field and the estimation of its parameters. At the last iterations it is ready to compute the MPM.

5. Implementation details

Though substantially automatic and unsupervised, the method still presents some implementation details that should be clarified for the sake of reproducibility. These details are mainly related to the parameters associated with the resolution and acquisition characteristics of the working images, the hypersurface resolution that can be achieved in a practical scenario and the MRF joint simulation and estimation flux.

5.1. Geometric parameters

A 3D MRF on a 4D space has been presented in Section 3. Its dimensions are defined by the expression $\mathcal{S} = \mathcal{J} \times \mathcal{P} \times \mathcal{Q}$. At this point some considerations have to be made about the cardinality of these sets. A simple selection has been made in the case of the temporal set cardinality $|\mathcal{Q}|$. It is the total number of images in the cardiac cycle, so the field takes one site for each image in the cycle. For the LA direction, we have also taken one site per image. However, in this case, two limiting slices must be fixed to localize the LV, the ones corresponding to the apex and the base. The method assumes that the image acquisition protocol is application specific, so these slices are

Figure 4: Sampling sets for likelihood estimation.

determined by the technician during the programming of the MR pulse sequence (practically without any extra throughput). $|\mathcal{J}|$ is related to the mean endocardial radius (in mm) estimated in the myocardium annular fit, $\overline{\rho^{A,1}}$ (see Section A.3). We have chosen $|\mathcal{J}| = \pi \overline{\rho^{A,1}} / 8$.

As for the radial resolution, $|\mathcal{K}|$, and the radial extension, r_{\max} , of the field, they will conform, together with $|\mathcal{J}|$, the extension of the subsets from which the image information is extracted, as described in Fig. 3 and the resolution of the field, as presented in Fig. 2. The parameter r_{\max} is also related to the annular fit; specifically, $r_{\max} = 2\overline{\rho^{A,1}}$. For the radial resolution, we have selected the value $|\mathcal{K}| = 31$. The appearance of the field for this configuration of parameters is shown in Fig. 2. The segmentation results depend primarily on the selection of the parameter $|\mathcal{J}|$. We have observed that for values greater than two times the selected value, the epicardial segmentations are attracted to external structures. This could be alleviated by increasing the neighborhood order c , but at the cost of unaffordable computation times. A lower threshold exists for the parameter r_{\max} in order to include the whole myocardial region. The algorithm is stable as long as r_{\max} is larger than this threshold, but increasing the maximum radius increases the computational load. Additionally, the method is relatively stable to variations of $|\mathcal{K}|$, though a slight performance worsening has been observed for lower values than the one selected.

5.2. Parameter estimation and optimization

The joint parameter estimation and field simulation procedure, as implemented by the GSA, has to consider an initial configuration for the simulated fields (denoted \mathbf{K}_{11} and \mathbf{K}_{21}) as well as for the parameter vector (ν_0). Theoretically, any initial configuration should provide convergence to the law of the field. Nevertheless, different initial states lead to different amount of computational load, so in practice it is preferable to take a configuration with significant probability of occurrence in the searched law. In our case, taking into consideration that the prior parameters are unknown in the first step, we have sampled the field \mathbf{K}_2 according to the ML criterion and taken a sample of the field \mathbf{K}_1 uniformly in the configuration space. This choice implies that the weights of the prior are null in the first step, $\nu_0 = \mathbf{0}$. This way, likelihood terms have a greater influence at first iterations, giving more strength to smoothness

as the optimization process advances. This dynamic is in accordance with empirical optimization strategies as the one in Pluempitiwiriyawej et al. (2005), but in our case the parameters are free to evolve to their optimal estimates, which depend on the information available in the images and the geometric and dynamic cardiac features for a given patient.

The number of global simulations and parameter estimation steps in the algorithm is $T_{\text{SIM}} = 50$ from which the last $T_{\text{MPM}} = 5$ simulations have been used to estimate the MPM configuration of the field; see Winkler (1995). The number of simulations used to compute the expectations in (26) is $T_{\text{EXP}} = 10$, whereas $t_0 = 10$. Finally, the constant B in the stochastic gradient algorithm has been selected according to the rules given in Younes (1989), so it depends on the log-likelihood gradient modulus by $B = 20|\nabla \log(f(\mathbf{I}; \nu))|$ and, consequently, it varies with t .

6. Results

This Section presents the most important experiments that have been carried out. On the whole, they serve for the validation, justification and evaluation of the method. First, the clinical interest of the method is established by the comparison of errors in the measures of physiological parameters with other published results. Second, the measurement errors are analyzed spatially and also compared with results in the literature. Third, the parameter estimation empirical behavior is analyzed. Finally, we present the experiments carried out on the difficult problem of basal slice determination.

We have considered a sample of 43 cine echo-like steady-state free precession MRI cardiac acquisitions performed inside a clinical environment of patients previously affected by an AMI. The images have been acquired with a GE Genesis Signa 1.5 T equipment. All of them have dimension 512×512 with a number of slices ranging from 12 to 17. Their resolution is $0.86 \times 0.86 \times 8 \text{ mm}^3$ with a slice thickness of 7 mm in one case and 6 mm in the remaining, so in all cases they present a certain slice gap. 18 images were acquired throughout the cardiac cycle in four cases and 20 images in the rest of cases. Echo time varies in the range 1.312 – 1.408 ms and repetition time varies in 3.256 – 3.444 ms, whereas flip angles are of 45° . The patients average heart rates during the acquisition are 59.81 ± 9.38 beats per minute, their ages are 61.65 ± 9.97 years and their

weights are 76.28 ± 7.89 kg. The patient set is composed of 39 males and 4 females. The interest of the method is justified in the necessity of precise and reproducible results for LV function measures as these measures are a source of information in which conclusions about patient diagnosis and treatment could rely. As the results presented in this paper correspond to a pilot study for the evaluation of a stem cell therapy, some acquisitions can only be considered as tuning steps of the subsequent randomized study, so, in general, they may endure more sources of variability.

6.1. Physiological validation

Four physiological parameters have been measured from the results of the segmentation method: the EDV, the ESV, the EF and the MM at ED. The reason for this parameter choice is the fact that the cardiologist has only segmented the endocardial contours at both ED and ES and the epicardial contour at ED, so these are the main parameters that we can compare. Our main results are summarized in Table 1, whereas in Table 2 a comparison is performed with some methods in the literature. In general, our measures are comparable to those reported by other studies and no method seems to be particularly outstanding. The advantage of our method relies on being the only so far reported method to be simultaneously automatic, unsupervised and applied to pathological cases. In addition, it seems to outperform the results for MM measurement in the literature, although differences are not significant mainly due to the high variance in the reported measures. It is also important to note that the EF and MM errors are comparable to the intra-operator ranges for manual contouring reported in Sardanelli et al. (2008). Additionally, p -values of a two-tailed paired t -test with unknown but equal variances of the manual and automatic physiological parameters measures are reported in Table 1. Those values show that the hypothesis of equality of their means cannot be rejected at a 0.05 significance level.

Plots of the linear regression of the measured parameters and those derived from the experts are shown in Fig. 6 whereas the corresponding Bland-Altman plots are shown in Fig. 7. The EDV measures seem to be slightly more precise than those of the ESV (in terms of relative error; i.e., see the column of the coefficient of variation in Table 1). This could be due to the fact that the diastolic motion pattern is generally softer. This way, the EDV measures are influenced by a more stable information content, so they are indeed more stable. Nevertheless, the overall effect of ESV inaccuracies in the EF calculation is negligible, showing the ability of our method to get a consistent dynamic evolution of the contours throughout the cardiac cycle. The inaccuracies in the calculation of the MM at ED are biased by the EDV computations and the difficult task of segmenting the epicardial boundary. The presence of outliers in the measures is mainly due to the segmentation of most basal and apical slices. The most basal slices are difficult to segment because of the low resolution in the LA axis and the changes in the topology of the cavity, whereas in the most apical slices less information is available. Despite this, the results remain in acceptable ranges.

6.2. Distribution of the segmentation errors

In this Section we perform a deeper analysis of the segmentation results by taking into account the spatial distribution of their errors. For each surface segmented both manual and automatically, we divide the myocardium in the 16 zones standardized in Cerqueira et al. (2002) (excluding the apical cap). For that purpose, we take the manually segmented surface and divide its longitudinal extension in 3 segments of the same size. These correspond approximately to the apical, medial and basal zones. Then, for the apical zone, we build 4 different sectors as the regions limited by 2 rays oriented at 45° and 135° . For the medial and basal zones we build 6 sectors as the regions limited by 3 rays oriented at 0° , 60° and 120° . Finally, the surfaces are clipped for each of the 16 zones obtained and the undirected distances between the resulting surface patches are computed on the basis of the Danielsson distance (Danielsson, 1980). As a reference, a diagram of this partition, known as bull's eye view, is shown in Fig. 8.

In Fig. 9 the boxplots of the results for the endocardium at ED are presented. The boxes represent the lower quartile, median and upper quartile values; the whiskers represent the whole extension of the error distribution whereas the crosses correspond to outliers. The largest errors are located mainly at the lateral zone due to the presence of the papillary muscles⁵. The global error distribution shows the presence of one outlier, whereas the remaining segmentations have mean errors lower than approximately 1.5 mm. In the case of Hausdorff distance errors, largest values are located at the basal slices mainly due to the absence of myocardial tissue at the most basal and septal locations. It should be noted that these results are not a limitation of the segmentation method, but a systematic error inherent to the SA acquisition of the images, which entails a lower resolution in the LA axis and therefore an imprecise localization of the mitral valve. Fig. 10 shows the same results for the endocardium at ES. In this case larger mean errors are also located at the free wall. On the other hand, there are no outliers for the global mean errors. Regarding the epicardium errors at ED shown in Fig. 11, results are similar to those of the endocardium at ED, which is in accordance with the MT coupling restrictions included in the method.

The mean error of our method is also in the ranges presented in the literature as shown in Table 3, where our method stands within the leading group. Moreover, the std. error remains for the endocardium and the epicardium as the first and second lowest respectively, which reveals the stability of the method presented.

A comparison is shown in Table 4 to indicate the stability of the method against varying degrees of infarction. The 16 standard zones of the myocardium are labeled by a cardiologist into normal, hypokinetic, akinetic and dyskinetic contractility. As

⁵Contours drawn by the experts include papillary muscles in the interior of the LV cavity; our algorithm is designed to that end too since the regularization terms of the field tend to pull the contour out of the papillary muscles. However, if at some slice these muscles are small enough and intensities agree with those expected, regularization terms might not succeed and a bias could appear, specially if this error extends to adjacent slices.

Table 1: Physiological parameters validation results.

Parameter	bias error	std. error	rms error	mean abs. error	max abs. error	coef. var.	ρ	p
EDV (cm ³)	-3.57	8.25	8.99	6.97	22.19	0.05	0.98	0.699
ESV (cm ³)	-3.34	7.24	7.98	6.32	23.28	0.09	0.98	0.658
EF (%)	1.49	3.32	3.64	3.07	7.72	0.06	0.96	0.510
ED MM (gr)	8.25	11.61	12.24	12.12	29.75	0.11	0.88	0.186

Table 2: Errors (mean \pm std.) in the measurement of physiological parameters. Comparison with other approaches. The p -value of a bilateral t -test with unknown and different variances at 0.05 level (0.025 at each side) is shown in parentheses when differences are found significant.

Reference	EDV (cm ³)	ESV (cm ³)	EF (%)	ED MM (gr)	Methodology	Comments
van der Geest et al. (1997)	-5.5 \pm 9.7	-3.6 \pm 6.5	1.7 \pm 4.1	7.3 \pm 20.6	See Section 1.1.3	10 patients / 10 healthy subjects; 3 excluded
Nachtomy et al. (1998)	-15.3 \pm 13.4 (0.0007)	-10.0 \pm 14.2	0.8 \pm 6.8	27.1 \pm 39.5 (0.0241)	See Section 1.1.1	10 patients / 10 healthy subjects
Avedisijan et al. (1999)	-8.8 \pm 5.3 (0.0069)	-2.2 \pm 3.6	-0.9 \pm 3.1 (0.0153)	—	See Section 1.1.2	12 patients; semiautomatic corrections
Stegmann and Pedersen (2005)	-2.5 \pm 8.1	-0.8 \pm 4.5	-0.0 \pm 3.0	—	See Section 1.1.3	12 subjects
Corsi et al. (2006)	1 \pm 5 (0.0202)	-3 \pm 7	2 \pm 5.5	—	See Section 1.1.2	9 patients
Pednekar et al. (2006)	-1.8 \pm 11.7	-10.8 \pm 8.2 (0.0031)	7.6 \pm 5.6 (0.0007)	—	See Section 1.1.4	6 patients / 8 healthy subjects
Hautvast et al. (2006)	—	-0.8 \pm 5.5	1.7 \pm 6.8	—	See Section 1.1.2	69 subjects; ED segmented by the practitioner
van Geuns et al. (2006)	-8.1 \pm 11.5	-5.9 \pm 6.3	1.6 \pm 3.5	7.2 \pm 15.0	Fuzzy objects, smooth convex hull and radial minimum cost	7 patients / 3 healthy subjects
Mazonakis et al. (2010)	-6.1 \pm 7.2	-3.0 \pm 5.2	0.6 \pm 4.3	6.2 \pm 12.2	Bayesian flooding and weighted least-squares	18 patients; semiautomatic corrections
Ours	-3.6 \pm 8.2	-3.3 \pm 7.2	1.5 \pm 3.3	8.2 \pm 11.6	MRF based deformable model	43 patients previously affected by an AMI

our sample consists of only 43 patients, there are some regions where not all kinds of abnormal patterns are present (they are left blank in the table) or only one case exists (and therefore no std. is shown). Even though the study cannot be exhaustive due to this limitation, an ANOVA test reflects that, generally speaking, the segmentation performance remains stable for different levels of contractility. Indeed, if the ANOVA is calculated using the whole sample (i.e., data is collected from all the myocardial regions and errors are averaged among surfaces), a p -value of 0.336 is obtained; therefore, no significant differences would be found and hence we can conclude that the algorithm is fairly robust to differences in levels of contractility.

In order to assess the clinical feasibility of our segmentation method, a simple experiment has been conducted in which the regional EF and the global EF are used as features to classify the standard zones into normal and impaired. The classifier is trained with the decisions of the cardiologist by a leave-one-out procedure. Three classifiers are evaluated. The first one fits a normal distribution with common variances for each group, the second allows the variances to vary for each group, both of them with a pooled estimate of covariance, whereas the third uses Mahalanobis distances and different variances for each group. In all cases the manual and automatic segmentations present similar results. Best results are obtained with the classifier based on the Mahalanobis distance. Success rates were 81.7% and 83.0% respectively for the manual and automatic segmentations. These rates could probably be improved by the

Figure 8: Bull's eye view diagram. The zones are viewed from the apex to the base and the RV would stay at the left of the diagram.

addition of new features to the classifier but the sample for validation should be larger to avoid the overfitting problem.

Finally, visual segmentation results are presented in Fig. 12. It includes the segmentations for a basal, mid and apical slice both for ED and ES. Moreover, we also include a representation of the 3D model reconstructed from the segmentations. This visual representation helps in evaluating the regional MT by means of a scalar color field.

Figure 6: Regression plots of the physiological parameters measurement.

6.3. Evaluation of the parameter estimation

In Section 4.3 a method for the estimation of the MRF parameters was presented. The purpose of this Section is to justify the parameter evolution and convergence and to clarify some additional implementation details. The large number of parameters involved and the stochastic nature of the estimation procedure prevents from an exhaustive analysis of the estimated parameters. The convergence of the prior parameters can be controlled by a proper selection of B and t_0 —recall (26). In their selection we have taken into account that for the simultaneous parameter estimation and hypersurface optimization approach there is no 'true' parameter value and no guarantee of convexity for the likelihood function, so a notion of quasi-convergence must be established in which the weights of the stochastic gradient are used to control the stability of the parameter evolution. The key

idea is that if the parameters return infinitely often to a bounded space, then they converge (Younes, 1989). In our method, the parameter estimation is used to obtain satisfactory segmentation results. Although hints of convergence can be observed in the parameter evolution curves, the actual convergence, if achieved, would entail an unfeasible computation time, so it is not pursued in our algorithm

A set of experiments have been performed that compare the segmentation errors obtained for different assumptions in the parameter estimation approach and consequently in the design of the field in order to justify the parameter estimation. The results are summarized in Table 5. The first experiment considers the case in which the estimation and the simulation are not implemented. Then, the segmentation solution is the starting configuration of the field. The results have a great bias and variance

Figure 7: Bland-Altman plots of the physiological parameters measurement.

as the likelihood modeling by itself is not able to represent precisely the myocardium geometric and dynamic features. In the second experiment, the structure of the MRF is degenerated to the site independence assumption. The results are similar to the first case as the field has a relatively uniform distribution in the configuration space and the MPM estimator is not well suited to this situation. Finally, for comparison purposes, we repeat the results for the complete design. In this case we have observed that, due to the random nature of the algorithm, different executions provide somehow variable but plausible segmentation results.

6.4. Determination of the basal slice

Results reported so far have been obtained by taking for granted that the basal slice at ES is determined by the technician at acquisition time and this information is available for

processing. In this Section, to account for the case in which this information would not be at hand, we briefly address the problem of basal plane determination in a sequence of SA image acquisitions. First notice that the MRF-based segmentation by itself is unable to determine the LA location of this plane, as the grid dimensions are not allowed to vary in time. This is one of the major drawbacks of our technique, which is inherited from the limitations of the acquisition protocol. In the absence of dense LA information (which is our case) one has to resort to coarse approximations of the basal plane location. For that purpose, first, a procedure analogous to that of Sections A.2 and A.4 is implemented in which a FGMM is fitted to the intensity histogram inside the myocardium⁶. Second, the larger

⁶The initialization of the FGMM parameters is given by the results of Section A.4.

Table 3: Mean errors between surfaces (mean \pm std.). Comparison with other approaches. The p -value of a bilateral t -test with unknown and different variances at 0.05 level (0.025 at each side) is shown in parentheses when differences are found significant.

Reference	Endocardium (mm)	Epicardium (mm)	Methodology	Comments
Mitchell et al. (2002)	2.75 ± 0.86 ($< 10^{-4}$)	2.63 ± 0.76 ($< 10^{-4}$)	See Section 1.1.3	53 subjects from a set of 56
Kaus et al. (2004)	2.52 ± 0.98 ($< 10^{-4}$)	2.77 ± 1.07 ($< 10^{-4}$)	See Section 1.1.3	121 patients from a set of 169
van Assen et al. (2006)	1.97 ± 0.54 (0.0004)	2.23 ± 0.46 ($< 10^{-4}$)	See Section 1.1.3	15 healthy subjects; different views and acquisition protocols
Fradkin et al. (2008)	1.27 ± 0.54	1.56 ± 0.85 (0.0128)	See Section 1.1.2	35 patients; segmentation only at ED
Lu et al. (2009)	1.40 ± 1.18	1.75 ± 1.15 (0.0028)	See Section 1.1.4	41 subjects; segmentation both at ED and ES
Schaerer et al. (2010)	2.97 ± 0.38 ($< 10^{-4}$)	3.14 ± 0.33 ($< 10^{-4}$)	See Section 1.1.2	15 patients
Zhang et al. (2010)	1.69 ± 0.38 ($< 10^{-4}$)	1.89 ± 0.50 ($< 10^{-4}$)	See Section 1.1.3	25 healthy subjects / 25 patients
Zhu et al. (2010)	0.69 ± 0.13 ($< 10^{-4}$)	1.27 ± 0.18	See Section 1.1.3	22 subjects; propagation of manual segmentations at ED
Cousty et al. (2010)	1.42 ± 0.36	1.55 ± 0.23 ($< 10^{-4}$)	See Section 1.1.4	18 patients
Ours	1.37 ± 0.20	1.22 ± 0.17	MRF based deformable model	43 patients previously affected by an AMI

connected component of the myocardium for each slice is extracted. Third, the basal plane is determined by considering that it is orthogonal to the LA axis and goes through the point in the LA axis in which the LV cavity opens.

The result of this procedure is validated by the estimation of the myocardial mass change in the postprocessed model between ED and ES phases to see the degree in which it conforms with the myocardium incompressibility assumption. Swingen et al. (2004) present a study in which, based on this assumption, they prove the inaccuracies of 2D analysis. The MM change between ED and ES in 2D was $14.7 \pm 16.8\%$ whereas fusing the SA information with the one provided by a set of radial LA acquisitions, the differences were $0.1 \pm 9.1\%$. In our analysis a difference of $17.8 \pm 9.0\%$ is observed. This is in accordance with the results of their study, but it should be noted the important decrease in the std. of the difference, which seems to suggest that, despite of the intrinsic limitations of the 2D acquisition technique, the results are consistent throughout the cardiac cycle and on the patient sample.

7. Discussion

Some remarks should be made about the complexity of the method presented in order to help understand the implementation problems involved in the most sensitive parts of the algorithm. On the other hand it is also interesting to discuss the applicability of its results, which could more clearly bound the benefits of the method.

7.1. Computational complexity

Two experiments were carried out. One of them on a processing server machine with a $16 \times$ Quad Core AMD Opteron(tm) Processor 8350 at 1000 MHz (cache size of 512 KB and shared memory of 32 GB) and the other on a PC with a $2 \times$ Intel(R) Core(TM)2 Duo at 800 MHz (cache size of 4 MB and shared memory of 2 GB). The implementation is in C++ and uses

the toolkits VTK and ITK. The main processing steps of the method and their respective processing times are presented in Table 6. The total time in segmenting one 4D cardiac image has been 379 s (\approx 6 minutes) for the processing server and 3335 s (\approx 56 minutes) for the PC. The critical step that mostly affects the processing time of the algorithm is the joint optimization and parameter estimation of the MRF. The parameters with the deepest influence on the computational load are T_{SIM} , c and $|S|$. The computational complexity can be alleviated by using a partially parallel visiting schedule to the sites of the field (in which the set of sites of the field is partitioned into subsets of conditionally independent sites so the elements of these subsets can be updated in parallel) and a parallel parameter updating procedure. Indeed, in the processing server, mainly due to the parallel implementation of the simulation of the field, the computational load of this step remains in reasonable rates with respect to the rest of steps of the algorithm.

7.2. Potential usefulness of the method

The results show that the automatic segmentation procedure is in acceptable level of agreement with the manual segmentations. The main challenge on myocardial segmentation is to achieve an accurate measurement of the MM, which is an important indicator of mortality and morbidity. Reported inter-operator std. for this parameter in MR is 9.0 gr (Myerson et al., 2002) so our results do not seem to be away from those of manual segmentations. Regarding the cavity volume calculations at different phases of the cardiac cycle, it is important to consider that there exists a slight bias between automatic and manual segmentations. Nevertheless, as discussed in Steen et al. (2007), the most important point in the adoption of MR as a reference standard in the assessment of cardiac function is the consistency of the results obtained by a given analysis protocol. In this sense, the temporal coherence of the automatic method is suited for the purposes of repeatability and comparability of the measures. This property of our segmentation protocol has

Table 4: Mean segmentation errors (mean \pm std, expressed in mm) against varying levels of contractility for the zones shown in Fig. 8. p -values (p_1 and p_2) in the two rightmost columns are the result of two separate ANOVA tests: on column labelled p_1 the test is carried out using the data in the corresponding row whereas in p_2 column the test is carried out by averaging the error among surfaces.

Zone	Surface	Normal	Hypokinetic	Akinetic	Dyskinetic	p_1	p_2
Apex Lateral	Endocardium ED	1.66 \pm 0.55	1.47 \pm 0.41	1.94 \pm 0.49	2.08 \pm 0.42	0.285	0.236
	Epicardium ED	1.37 \pm 0.34	1.35 \pm 0.19	1.66 \pm 0.51	1.37 \pm 0.03	0.180	
	Endocardium ES	1.95 \pm 0.76	1.84 \pm 0.50	2.06 \pm 0.58	2.45 \pm 0.70	0.762	
Apex Anterior	Endocardium ED	1.39 \pm 0.41	1.98 \pm 0.55	1.55 \pm 0.31	2.08 \pm 0.40	0.007	0.003
	Epicardium ED	1.37 \pm 0.40	1.86 \pm 0.32	1.61 \pm 0.55	2.22 \pm 0.73	0.022	
	Endocardium ES	1.96 \pm 0.70	2.79 \pm 0.99	1.88 \pm 0.50	2.34 \pm 0.89	0.099	
Apex Septum	Endocardium ED	1.21 \pm 0.41	1.45 \pm 0.50	1.30 \pm 0.41	0.98 \pm 0.07	0.403	0.658
	Epicardium ED	1.05 \pm 0.32	1.15 \pm 0.42	1.30 \pm 0.20	0.86 \pm 0.14	0.132	
	Endocardium ES	1.53 \pm 0.52	1.52 \pm 0.60	1.54 \pm 0.56	1.74 \pm 1.02	0.963	
Apex Inferior	Endocardium ED	1.22 \pm 0.30	1.31 \pm 0.34	1.45 \pm 0.60	1.28 \pm 0.24	0.624	0.371
	Epicardium ED	1.28 \pm 0.28	1.38 \pm 0.41	1.20 \pm 0.18	1.27 \pm 0.11	0.380	
	Endocardium ES	1.51 \pm 0.23	1.99 \pm 1.14	1.79 \pm 0.52	1.65 \pm 0.24	0.423	
Mid Antero-Lateral	Endocardium ED	1.61 \pm 0.63	0.61	1.20 \pm 0.10	—	0.145	0.102
	Epicardium ED	1.29 \pm 0.38	1.09	1.48 \pm 0.43	—	0.551	
	Endocardium ES	3.15 \pm 1.31	1.43	2.70 \pm 1.03	—	0.360	
Mid Anterior	Endocardium ED	1.25 \pm 0.36	1.23 \pm 0.46	1.36 \pm 0.30	1.82 \pm 0.76	0.135	0.171
	Epicardium ED	1.29 \pm 0.52	1.30 \pm 0.38	1.28 \pm 0.42	2.27 \pm 1.40	0.053	
	Endocardium ES	2.45 \pm 1.32	1.45 \pm 0.55	1.93 \pm 0.86	1.76 \pm 0.64	0.186	
Mid Antero-Septum	Endocardium ED	1.14 \pm 0.37	1.15 \pm 0.56	1.14 \pm 0.24	1.34 \pm 0.24	0.912	0.410
	Epicardium ED	1.01 \pm 0.38	1.48 \pm 0.83	1.31 \pm 0.63	1.12 \pm 0.54	0.175	
	Endocardium ES	1.31 \pm 0.53	1.40 \pm 0.67	1.58 \pm 0.63	1.26 \pm 0.35	0.663	
Mid Infero-Septum	Endocardium ED	1.02 \pm 0.36	0.90 \pm 0.20	1.11 \pm 0.56	1.20	0.762	0.846
	Epicardium ED	1.05 \pm 0.43	1.02 \pm 0.21	1.01 \pm 0.05	0.86	0.973	
	Endocardium ES	1.14 \pm 0.46	1.42 \pm 0.49	1.43 \pm 0.15	1.53	0.382	
Mid Inferior	Endocardium ED	1.18 \pm 0.56	2.18 \pm 1.63	1.24 \pm 0.40	—	0.033	0.470
	Epicardium ED	1.58 \pm 0.68	1.21 \pm 0.39	1.82 \pm 0.67	—	0.461	
	Endocardium ES	1.77 \pm 0.72	2.02 \pm 0.50	1.93 \pm 0.22	—	0.758	
Mid Infero-lateral	Endocardium ED	1.51 \pm 0.62	0.64	1.44 \pm 0.49	—	0.381	0.265
	Epicardium ED	1.26 \pm 0.42	0.73	1.43 \pm 0.32	—	0.332	
	Endocardium ES	2.24 \pm 1.08	0.95	2.53 \pm 0.75	—	0.421	
Base Antero-Lateral	Endocardium ED	1.38 \pm 0.50	—	—	—	—	—
	Epicardium ED	1.39 \pm 0.57	—	—	—	—	
	Endocardium ES	2.20 \pm 0.82	—	—	—	—	
Base Anterior	Endocardium ED	1.64 \pm 0.57	2.71 \pm 1.00	—	—	0.016	0.431
	Epicardium ED	1.58 \pm 0.71	1.37 \pm 0.39	—	—	0.688	
	Endocardium ES	2.37 \pm 0.82	2.38 \pm 1.75	—	—	0.988	
Base Antero-Septum	Endocardium ED	1.71 \pm 0.97	—	—	—	—	—
	Epicardium ED	1.73 \pm 1.09	—	—	—	—	
	Endocardium ES	2.69 \pm 2.07	—	—	—	—	
Base Infero-Septum	Endocardium ED	1.31 \pm 0.65	0.95	—	—	0.593	0.929
	Epicardium ED	1.47 \pm 1.02	0.88	—	—	0.573	
	Endocardium ES	1.65 \pm 0.75	2.74	—	—	0.160	
Base Inferior	Endocardium ED	1.35 \pm 0.60	1.70 \pm 0.97	0.96 \pm 0.44	0.76	0.456	0.308
	Epicardium ED	1.49 \pm 0.59	1.83 \pm 1.49	1.43 \pm 0.83	1.86	0.800	
	Endocardium ES	1.87 \pm 0.91	2.12 \pm 1.44	1.65 \pm 0.34	0.65	0.576	
Base Infero-lateral	Endocardium ED	1.33 \pm 0.53	—	—	—	—	—
	Epicardium ED	1.55 \pm 0.92	—	—	—	—	
	Endocardium ES	2.57 \pm 1.09	—	—	—	—	

been illustrated in Section 6.1, in which we showed that the performance of our method was fairly close to that of the manual segmentation we had access to (taking into account the values for inter-operator variability reported in the literature). Moreover, in some cases, the continuity of the surface throughout the cardiac cycle could provide more reliable results than the practitioners segmentation, as manually checking the temporal coherence of the contours they mark in ED and ES is clearly cumbersome. The error in the calculation of the EDV and ESV is mainly due to the interpretation of the papillary muscles which, in some situations, may be different in the algorithm than in the medical protocol adopted by the practitioner, but coherent in both cases. This coherence is proved by the excellent agreement in the EF measures.

Nevertheless, the proposed segmentation method is not limited to the calculation of these functional global parameters.

Temporal and spatial dependent measures could also be obtained. From these, the analysis and visualization of regional contractility is essential to provide a clinical tool with all the required functionalities in the conventional practice. Qualitative and quantitative contractility indicators can be extracted from the segmentations (mainly from the thickening of the myocardial wall) and presented to the cardiologist by coloring the surface superimposed onto the images, so that the expert can fast and easily focus the attention on the injured zone. Moreover, the temporal evolution of the surfaces could also be employed to improve the depth of analysis of LV motion.

The automatism of the method and its independence from a cohort of previously analyzed images must be interpreted not as a denial of the opposite, but as an attempt to justify the adaptability of the method. Interactive user assistance could be adopted in the generation of the initial model and informa-

Figure 9: Spatial distribution of errors for the endocardium at ED.

Table 5: Evaluation of the design. Errors (mean \pm std.) obtained for different assumptions in the model.

Assumption	EDV (cm ³)	ESV (cm ³)	EF (%)	ED MM (gr)
$T_{SIM} = 0$	4.60 \pm 12.00	10.35 \pm 13.05	-4.28 \pm 5.55	26.19 \pm 16.45
$c = 0$	4.93 \pm 13.06	10.13 \pm 12.09	-4.11 \pm 4.63	27.67 \pm 19.90
Complete	-3.57 \pm 8.25	-3.34 \pm 7.24	1.49 \pm 3.32	8.25 \pm 11.61

tion from an atlas of segmented hearts could be integrated in the MRF framework. Both of them could make the method faster and improve its results since the search space of the deformed surfaces can be restricted to a smaller volume and the atlas information can be integrated optimally by estimating its likelihood. However, the integration of these factors must ensure the reproducibility of the results, so studies of sensitivity to these factors should be incorporated to the validation procedure. Additionally, given a set of representative models, our method could attempt the segmentation of parts of the heart with a more intricate geometry, such as that of the RV, with assumptions analogous to the ones performed in this paper. The method also admits a relatively direct 3D extension. This extension seems even more pertinent given the advances in the acquisition techniques for cardiac MRI (Kozerke et al., 2004). The main decision to confront for this extension is the selection of the coordinate system from which to build the MRF. It seems that a prolate spheroidal MRF model could be the most natural extension.

8. Conclusion

An automated and unsupervised method for the segmentation of the LV in SA cardiac MR images has been presented and validated. The method has proven to be a powerful resource for the

segmentation of the myocardium throughout the cardiac cycle. The clinical environment in which the method has been validated is a fundamental issue to guarantee the applicability of the results to studies of cardiac function recovery, where precise, repeatable and reliable measures of image-derived parameters are determinant factors to conclude the viability of different therapies. In this sense, although some measures are biased with respect to the ones derived from the segmentations of a experienced cardiologist, there is a good level of agreement between them, the results have proven to be robust in a representative patient set and they could be used for diagnostic purposes. Though computationally expensive, the method is an attempt to provide a framework for adaptive segmentation of images. This adaptivity comes from the unsupervised estimation of the parameters of a MRF that models the segmentation problem. Image information is integrated with spatio-temporal surface smoothness in a way that depends on the intrinsic characteristics of the image under analysis and the anatomical and functional configuration of the myocardium for each patient, a property that is not present in most existing deformable model methods.

Figure 10: Spatial distribution of errors for the endocardium at ES.

Table 6: Decomposition of the computation times of the method. The times are represented in seconds respectively for the PC and the processing server. In those cases in which parallel computation is used, the time refers to the real spent time and not the cpu time.

Myocardium detection				MRF segmentation		
1017/107				2318/272		
CC detection	CC modeling	LV detection	LV modeling	Likelihood modeling	MRF modeling	Optimization
29/5	30/16	941/76	17/10	213/33	538/78	1567/161

A. Myocardium detection

This Appendix describes the technique for the detection of the myocardium in MRI and the generation of the inputs for the MRF-based segmentation algorithm, namely the centers of the LV in each SA slice, $C[p]$, and the label image L from which masks are built to estimate the parameters of the likelihood distributions. The procedure is based in the hierarchical confinement of the search space for the myocardium. The technique requires the suitable adjustment of a small set of parameters (whose values, which have been the same for all the images used in the experiments, are specified throughout this Appendix) so at the end of each step some considerations are performed which explain their tuning. Methods based on the registration of a cardiac model to the images could be used instead (Zhuang et al., 2010), but we have resorted to the method here described in order to keep our segmentation procedure completely unsupervised.

A.1. CC detection

Sorgel and Vaerman (1997) describe a method for the detection of the CC. The final objective of their procedure is to serve for the automatic initial placement of contours for AC segmentation methods. In our case the objective of the CC detection

is the appropriate selection of the image region from which to extract a representative sample of the tissues involved in the segmentation problem. In what follows, we pay attention to the main differences between the two methods which, indeed, share a similar overall structure.

The main steps of our detection method are summarized in the block-diagram of Fig. 13. Both the method in Sorgel and Vaerman (1997) and ours use the temporal standard deviation of the image pixels as the detection feature for the CC. Their major differences are concentrated on the postprocessing required to achieve the desired robustness for this detection feature. Prior to the calculation of the temporal standard deviation the background of the image is suppressed. For that purpose, the ED phase is extracted, the dynamic range of the data is compressed by a logarithmic mapping, then it is smoothed by a Gaussian kernel with standard deviation $\sigma_G = 65$ mm and finally a binary image is generated by the Otsu threshold segmentation method. This method separates the histogram in two regions maximizing the inter-class variance, so it is suited to binarize images with bimodal histograms.

An analogous procedure serves to detect the cardiac cavity. The temporal standard deviation is computed in the pixels given by the non-background region and using the original intensity range, the image is smoothed with a Gaussian kernel with stan-

Figure 11: Spatial distribution of errors for the epicardium at ED.

dard deviation $\sigma_G = 65$ mm and a Otsu threshold segmentation is performed. In Sorgel and Vaerman (1997), the threshold is determined by computing the binarization for different candidate thresholds and taking the one that maximizes the relation between the largest connected component area and the sum of the areas of the remaining connected components. Besides the greater computational load involved in the binarization and area calculations for the set of candidate thresholds, the selection of the final threshold is achieved by the multiplication of the best candidate threshold by a factor ϵ in the range $1 \leq \epsilon \leq 2$, so the method is somewhat involved and heuristic.

Consequently, the CC detection only depends on one parameter, σ_G . We have visually observed that there is a lower threshold for an optimal detection about 60 mm. The detection is robustly performed for larger values, but there is an increasing risk of including pixels outside the CC. Taking into account the large value of this parameter, the Gaussian smoothing is based in the approximate recursive implementation proposed in Deriche (1990).

A.2. CC tissue modeling

The intensity of the pixels inside the CC region is sampled to build a cardiac histogram. Under the assumption of high SNR, it is suitable to model the intensity of MRI as a Gaussian distribution (Sijbers et al., 1998). Different tissues will generate different Gaussian components, so a FGMM is adequate to model the distribution of pixel intensities. The problem of determining the optimal number of components is involved, specially taking into account the PVE so we have set this number to 3, expecting to find air, muscle and blood as the main constituents of the cardiac tissues. Another problem is the intensity inhomogeneity often present in MRI (Vovk et al., 2007). We have resorted

to an intensity normalization similar to the one presented in Peters et al. (2010). Specifically, the intensity distribution of each SA 2D+T image is normalized to the percentile 0.95.

The EM algorithm has been used to estimate the parameters of the model with a deterministic initialization given by $\alpha_{\{A,M,B\}} = 1/3$, $\mu_A = 0$, $\mu_M = 0.2$, $\mu_B = 0.8$, $\sigma_A = 0.0025$, $\sigma_M = 0.01$ and $\sigma_B = 0.04$; each one referring respectively to the likelihoods, means and standard deviations for the different components. The final parameters allow for the ML estimation of the pixel tissues \mathbf{L}' . Background, air, muscle and blood are respectively labelled by $l = \{0, 1, 2, 3\}$.

The normalization percentile and the initial parameters of the EM algorithm have been selected based on the visual inspection of the histogram of a randomly selected image.

A.3. LV detection

For each SA slice p , $L'[m, n, p, 0]$ is registered with an annulus-shaped kernel whose values correspond to the labels for the blood and muscle tissue. It has a functional form depending on its center \mathbf{C}_A and its inner and outer radii $\rho^{A,1}$ and $\rho^{A,2}$

$$L^A(\rho_{\mathbf{C}_A}^A) = \begin{cases} 3 & \text{if } \rho_{\mathbf{C}_A}^A < \rho^{A,1}, \\ 2 & \text{if } \rho^{A,1} \leq \rho_{\mathbf{C}_A}^A < \rho^{A,2}. \end{cases} \quad (27)$$

The metric for registration is based on Kappa statistics. Let \mathbf{L}_3^A and \mathbf{L}_2^A denote the subsets of pixels labeled as blood and muscle in the kernel and by \mathbf{L}'_3 and \mathbf{L}'_2 the ones with the corresponding labels from the ML estimator. Then the metric β is defined by

$$\beta = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{l \in \{2,3\}} \frac{|\mathbf{L}'_l \cap \mathbf{L}_l^A|}{|\mathbf{L}_l^A|} \quad (28)$$

Figure 12: Visual results of the algorithm.

The configuration of annulus parameters that gives the maximum metric value for each SA image at ED is adopted as an initial fit for the LV.

The parameters of the kernel are $[C_0^A, C_1^A, \rho^{A,1}, \rho^{A,2}]$. In order to obtain the maximum value of the metric, they are allowed to vary in a discrete space given by $C_u^A = C_u^{\text{FOV}} + \tau_0 \Delta$, $\rho^{A,1} = o_1 + \tau_1 \Delta$, $\rho^{A,2} = \rho^{A,1} + o_2 + \tau_2 \Delta$, with C_u^{FOV} the center of the Field of View of the SA images, $u = \{0, 1\}$ indexes a space dimension, $\Delta = 2$ is the resolution of the discretization, $-25 \leq \tau_0 \leq 25$, $o_1 = 5$, $0 \leq \tau_1 \leq 18$, $o_2 = 4$ and $0 \leq \tau_2 \leq 6$. The search around C_u^{FOV} is justified by the fact that the center of the Field of View of SA images roughly coincides with the LV center. The method runs sequentially from the base to the apex. Closeness of adjacent LV centers is guaranteed by an additional condition:

$$|C_u^A[p+1] - C_u^A[p]| \leq \tau_3,$$

with $\tau_3 = 20$. The method is relatively robust to small changes in the parameters o_1 and o_2 and the ranges of τ_0 , τ_1 and τ_2 , assuming they are close to the myocardial dimensions. Finally, the parameter τ_3 should balance the fact that excessively small values miss interslice jumps of the LV center that may arise from motion artifacts or bending of the LA axis and excessively large values decrease the robustness of the detection and intro-

Figure 13: CC detection. The method detects the torso (upper row) and then the CC (lower row). The procedure is analogous in both cases. It primes robustness at the expense of precision as this is a preliminary stage in the processing of cardiac images.

duce computational overload. Regarding the sensitivity with respect to the parameter Δ , we have observed that the segmentation results used for physiological measurement remain stable up to approximately $\Delta = 6$ (as for larger values the LV detection fails at the apical slices), so arguably the segmentation results remain reasonably stable with respect to inaccuracies in the LV center detection⁷.

A.4. LV tissue modeling

This stage generates two parameters that characterize the myocardial region, namely, a center given by $C[p]$ and a radius given by $\bar{\rho}^{A,1} = \sum_p \rho^{A,1*}[p]/|\mathcal{P}|$, which is common for all slices.

The model is analogous to that of Section A.2 except that in this case the starting parameters are the ones obtained in Section A.2 and the slice intensity normalization is slightly different: 10 iterations of the EM algorithm are run for each SA slice separately and $\mu_M[p]$ is used as the renormalization factor. The model results in the ML tissue labeling \mathbf{L} used in Section 4.2.2 for the estimation of likelihood parameters.

B. Symbols

Table 7: Symbols used through the text

Symbol	Description
$I[b]$	Intensity image at a given pixel
\mathbf{I}	Vector of intensities over all pixels
\mathbf{b}	Index of a pixel of the image
m	Index of a SA row
n	Index of a SA column
p	Index of a SA slice (discrete version of z)
q	Index of a cardiac phase (discrete version of ϕ)

⁷Values in this Section are given in pixels.

C	Center of the LV
r	Radius in the SA plane
ψ	Angle in the SA plane
z	Coordinate in the LA direction
ϕ	Temporal coordinate
r^1	SA radius for the endocardium
r^2	SA radius for the epicardium
j	Index of a SA ray (discrete version of ψ)
$ \mathcal{J} $	Total number of rays
$ \mathcal{P} $	Total number of SA slices
$ \mathcal{Q} $	Total number of cardiac phases
k	Index of a SA radius
k^1	Index of the endocardial radius
k^2	Index of the epicardial radius
$ \mathcal{K} $	Total number of radius
r_{\max}	Maximum radius allowed
s	Site of the field
S	Set of sites
K	Random vector of the field
\mathcal{K}'	Set of possible configurations for a random variable of the field
Ω	Space of configurations of the field
k	Realization of the field
$\Pi(\mathbf{k})$	Law of the field
$\delta(\mathbf{s})$	Neighborhood system of the field
c	Order of the neighborhood
Z	Partition function of the field
C	Clique induced by the neighborhood system
\mathcal{C}	Set of cliques induced by the neighborhood system
$V_{\mathcal{C}}(\mathbf{k})$	Potential function of the field over a given clique
$U_{\mathcal{C}}(\mathbf{k})$	Normalized potential function of the field over a given clique
$\nu_{\mathcal{C}}$	Parameter of the field prior for a given clique
$f(\mathbf{I} \mathbf{k})$	Likelihood function of the data given a configuration of the field
a	Coordinate vector. Used as a shortcut for (ψ, z, ϕ) .
i	Index of the set of restrictions imposed to the field (referring to endocardium, epicardium and myocardial thickness)
u, v	Index of coordinates
D	Descriptor extracted from the image (intensity or gradient)
w	Index of descriptors
y	Index of types of zones of the myocardium (referring to region and boundary)
∇	Gradient operator
ε	Subset of the image consisting of an angular sector
γ	Subset of pixels that conform a given zone of the myocardium
$g(x)$	Gaussian distribution
μ	Mean of the Gaussian distribution
σ	Standard deviation of the Gaussian distribution

d	Index of types of intensity transitions
T	Random variable of the type of transition in the myocardial boundaries
MB	Muscle-blood transition
MA	Muscle-air transition
$e(x)$	Exponential distribution
λ	Rate parameter of the exponential distribution
$h(x)$	Gamma distribution
θ	Scale parameter of the gamma distribution
κ	Shape parameter of the gamma distribution
M	Sampling mask image
L	Label image in the surroundings of the LV
l	Label index
\mathbf{k}^*	MPM configuration of the field
\mathbf{v}^*	ML parameter vector of the field
t	Index of simulations of the field
B	Constant to ensure convergence in parameter estimation
t_0	Constant to modulate the weight in the stochastic gradient algorithm
T_{EXP}	Number of simulations of the field used to compute the expectations
$\overline{\rho^{A,1}}$	Mean endocardial radius obtained in the annular fit
T_{SIM}	Total number of simulations of the field
T_{MPM}	Number of simulations of the field used to compute the MPM
ρ	Correlation coefficient
ϵ	Thresholding factor in Sorgel and Vaerman (1997)
σ_G	Standard deviation of the Gaussian smoothing kernel used for detection
$\alpha_{A,M,B}$	Likelihood of air/muscle/blood tissues
$\mu_{A,M,B}$	Intensity mean of air/muscle/blood tissues
$\sigma_{A,M,B}$	Intensity standard deviation of air/muscle/blood tissues
L'	Label image for the CC
L^A	Label image for the annular template
C^A	Center of the annular template
ρ^A	Radius of the annular template
β	Metric for LV detection
C^{FOV}	Center of the Field of View for SA images
Δ	Resolution of the discretization for LV detection
τ	Dimension of the search space for LV detection
o	Origin of the search space for LV detection

Acknowledgments

This work was partially supported by the Fondo de Investigaciones Sanitarias under Research Grant PI04-1483, Ministerio de Ciencia e Innovación and the Fondo Europeo de Desarrollo Regional (FEDER) under Research Grant TEC2007-67073/TCM, and by the Centro para el Desarrollo Tecnológico Industrial (CDTI) under the cvREMODO project and Research Grant CEN-20091044. The work was also funded by the Junta de Castilla y León under Grants VA027A07 and VA039A10-2, and the Consejería de Sanidad de Castilla y León under Grants GRS 292/A/08, SAN126/VA032/09 and SAN126/VA033/09.

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